

Comparing hybrid and machine learning models for rainfall-induced shallow landslide susceptibility.

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Abstract— Effective risk management for rainfall-induced mass movements necessitates models that simultaneously have predictive power and are interpretable. This study introduces a hybrid model combining machine learning and physical principles to enhance landslide susceptibility predictions under rainfall conditions. By integrating the predictive power of machine learning with an infinite-slope stability approach, we overcome traditional limitations in model parametrization. We utilized static and dynamic key factors such as terrain surface properties, lithological and tectonic setting, land cover/land use and accumulated precipitation to estimate effective cohesion, internal friction angle and soil parameters as latent variables of a Factor-of-Safety model based on the law of Mohr-Coulomb. We compared this approach with established physically-based and empirical models for a landslide/non-landslide point sample of 620 observations in a study area in northern and western Slovenia (400km²) where disastrous rainfall events happened in August and autumn 2023. A spatial block cross-validation yielded median Area under the Receiver Operating Curve values of 0.53 for the physical model, 0.85 for the benchmark empirical model and 0.66 for the hybrid model. Despite inferior model performance in discriminating between landslide and non-landslide points compared to the benchmark, the hybrid model allows for the interpretation, mapping and plausibility check of geomechanical and hydrological slope stability parameters.

I. INTRODUCTION

Rainfall triggered landslides pose a significant threat to communities worldwide. Models that accurately predict landslide susceptibility can allow for more effective planning and risk management strategies.

Machine learning models have proven their predictive power in modelling landslide susceptibility, as they are capable of effectively capturing patterns and trends in large datasets without relying on explicit physical equations. Physically-based models,

by contrast, reflect the underlying geomechanical and hydrological slope processes more plausibly. However, they require sophisticated parametrization through field work and laboratory testing and are not easily transferable from individual slopes to the regional-scale susceptibility mapping for spatial planning purposes.

In recent years, in an attempt to overcome the drawbacks of each of the modelling approaches, researchers successfully developed physically constrained machine learning models in the Earth system sciences [1,2]. The seminal paper by Reichstein et al. [3] provides an overview on how physical knowledge and machine learning techniques can be interlinked.

Following this paradigm we have developed a machine-learning approach that is constrained by a hybrid infinite-slope stability model. In comparison with traditional approaches to the parametrization of physically-based models, we use machine learning to estimate model parameters as latent variables by fitting the physical and machine learning part simultaneously.

We compared this hybrid, physically-informed machine learning approach with a traditional Factor-of-Safety model, and with established machine learning models (Generalized Additive Model, GAM) with the influence of dynamic predictors (antecedent rainfall) in terms of predictive performance.

II. STUDY AREA

The study area of 400km² comprises three Slovenian municipalities located in those regions which have been most severely struck by flooding and rainfall-triggered mass movements after a rainfall event in August 2023 [4,5], and, to a lesser extent, in October and November 2023. Landslide data has been mapped in the field and from remote sensing data by GeoZS; mapping in other affected regions is still ongoing.

The neighbouring municipalities Ravne na Koroškem and Slovenj Gradec are located in north-central Slovenia at the border to Austria. The landscape is dominated by mountainous terrain and an inner alpine valley with alluvial sediment. Železniki in north-eastern Slovenia lies in the Southern Alps and their hilly karst forelands.

The complex lithology is governed by a tectonic setting in the border zone between the Dinarides and the Southern and Eastern Alps. In the Southern Alps and in the karstic area, limestones, dolomites and complex alternating sedimentary rocks prevail; metamorphic and volcanic rock types are predominant in the Eastern Alps. Especially the alternating sedimentary rocks are susceptible to landsliding.

Climate ranges from temperate-humid to alpine at higher elevations with maritime influence by the Mediterranean sea.

From August 3rd to 5th 2023, northern Slovenia was hit by severe rainfall with cumulative precipitation of more than 300mm within 72 hours, following an exceptionally wet period in May – July. This led to flooding and triggered mass movements such as debris flows and shallow landslides and caused fatalities and damage to infrastructure. The study area is located in the most affected areas. At the end of October and beginning November 2023 another series of rainfall events triggered further landslides in the study region, however to a lesser extent than in summer 2023.

III. DATA AND METHODS

An inventory of landslide initiation points was compiled by GeoZS in a field survey and satellite-based mapping campaign shortly after the events. After the exclusion of areas flatter than a slope angle of 5°, 310 landslide initiation points were left for fitting the model. We randomly selected 310 non-landslide points in the study area with a minimum separation distance of 500m from the identified landslide points to account for the typical areal extent of shallow landslides, resulting in a total of 620 training points.

We generated a 10m digital elevation model (DEM) from a LiDAR point cloud with 1m ground resolution. We calculated slope angle, slope aspect, longitudinal and cross-sectional curvature after [6] as well as upslope contributing area and topographic wetness index (TWI) with a multiple flow direction algorithm [7] with SAGA GIS modules.

We calculated the distance of every landslide initiation point to active and probably active tectonic faults and reduced a lithological map to five classes of mineral types with similar mechanic properties. We reclassified Land Cover and Land Use (LULC) data to four classes. The datasets were provided by GeoZS.

For the northern part of Slovenia, integrated nowcast precipitation (INCA) data from Geosphere Austria is available. We aggregated hourly rainfall amounts to cumulative precipitation one day and 2-5 days before the landslide occurred.

As machine-learning benchmark models, we fitted a logistic GAM [8] with lithology and LULC as linear predictors and smoothing terms for topographic and tectonic variables and dynamic rainfall amounts. As our physically-based benchmark, following [9,10] we calibrated a Factor-of-Safety model where we consider bulk dry soil density ρ and a transmissivity-to-recharge ratio T/R as indicators for pore water pressure

$$FS = \frac{C' + \cos(\beta) \tan(\phi') \frac{1 - a/(\sin(\beta) T/R)}{\rho}}{\sin(\beta)}$$

with effective cohesion C' , and effective friction angle ϕ' as well as ρ and T/R as unknown model parameters at each landslide initiation point. The local slope angle β and upslope contributing area a are given at each location. In the literature on infinite slope model calibration, C' is commonly assumed to be zero and stabilizing forces are attributed solely to the friction angle. Instead, in our model, we calibrated all model parameters for physical plausibility and comparability.

In the hybrid framework, we conceptualized the parameters C' , ϕ' , T/R and ρ as latent variables. Each of them was represented by a linear combination, or weighted sum, of terrain properties, LULC, geological units and precipitation. This hybrid Factor-of-Safety model was fitted with landslide occurrence as target variable.

We estimated model performance with spatial block k-fold cross validation with six folds and ten repetitions, resulting in a total of 60 training/test set splits. A comparison between spatial and non-spatial (random with 60 splits) cross-validation errors allowed for an assessment of the ability to generalize the modelled relationships. We used the Receiver Operating Curve (ROC) and the area under this curve (AUC) to compare the models' ability to discriminate between landslide and non-landslide initiation points.

We used R 4.3.3 with mgcv, SAGA GIS 9.5.1 for terrain model preprocessing and CloudCompare v2.12.x. All data was projected into EPSG:3794 Slovene National Grid 1996.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Looking at model performance (fig. 1), preliminary results indicate that the hybrid model (median AUC 0.66) performs better than the physically-based slope stability model (median AUC 0.53, up to 0.68) but worse than the GAM (median AUC

0.85); all performance measures estimated by spatial block cross validation. However, the hybrid model is less prone to overfitting than the GAM, indicated by just a slight drop in model performance for the spatial CV compared to non-spatial CV.

In the hybrid model, physically meaningful parameters are estimated as latent variables. Compared to purely machine-learning approaches, those latent variables can be mapped in space. Each latent variable is estimated by a separate regression model which is interpretable with established statistical means. This allows checks for plausibility of each of the model coefficients and thus predictor influences.

Figure 1. Distribution of Area under the Receiver Operating Curve (AUC) values estimated by random and spatial block cross validation for: GAM random CV (median AUC 0.92), GAM spatial CV (median AUC 0.85), Hybrid random CV (median AUC 0.68) and Hybrid model spatial CV (median AUC 0.66).

V. OUTLOOK

The presented integration of physical with machine learning techniques in modelling rainfall-induced shallow landslide susceptibility demonstrates a robust and straightforward approach, achieving both satisfactory predictive power and interpretability.

Despite its effectiveness, opportunities for enhancement exist. Future work will focus on expanding the current linear regression model towards a more sophisticated non-linear modelling framework. Additionally, exploring the capabilities of more flexible artificial neural networks will offer a comparative assessment of model performance.

Given the significant influence of climate and weather dynamics on rainfall-induced landslide occurrence [11,12],

incorporating rainfall thresholds into a hybrid hazard model is imperative when aiming at an integrated early warning system.

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